

Synthesis of Pellitorine and Sarmentine— Alkamides isolated from *Piper sarmentosum*

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RECENTLY six compounds have been isolated¹ from the fruit of *Piper sarmentosum*. One of the constituents is a crystalline insecticidal unsaturated amide, pellitorine, established as *N*-isobutyl-(2*E*, 4*E*)-decadienamides (1), which has also been isolated² from *Anacyclus pyrenthum* DC as well as from a number of other *Piper* species, and other species belonging to the Compositae and Rutaceae families³. Amongst the new natural products isolated is an unsaturated pyrrolidine amide, sarmentine (2) which has been assigned the structure, *N*-(2*E*, 4*E*-decadienyl)pyrrolidine (2). Herein we report the facile synthesis of the title compounds pellitorine (1) and sarmentine (2) from a common intermediate (7).

The dianion of propargyl alcohol was alkylated⁴ with 1-bromopentane in liquid ammonia using lithium metal in the presence of catalytic amount of Fe(NO₃)₃ to give 2-octynol in 54% yield. The acetylenic bond in 3 was hydrogenated in the presence of Lindlar's catalyst⁵ to get 2-(*Z*)-octenol (4) which upon subsequent oxidation with pyridinium chlorochromate (PCC)⁶ in dry dichloromethane afforded 2-(*E*)-octenal (5) with complete isomerisation⁶ of the allylic *cis* double bond to more stable *trans* one. The ir spectrum of the conjugated aldehyde showed a characteristic band at 970 cm⁻¹ (*trans* double bond) and complete disappearance of a band at 870 cm⁻¹ (*cis* double bond). Condensation of 5 with the anion⁷ of dimethylethoxycarbonylmethyl phosphonate in dry THF produced (2*E*, 4*E*)-decadienoate (6) in 64% yield. The spectral data of the doubly conjugated ester is consistent with its structure. The conjugated ester 6 was hydrolysed with alcoholic KOH to produce the dienoic acid (7) in 70% yield.

Condensation of 7 with pyrrolidine and isobutylamine using POCl₃ in presence of excess triethylamine resulted in the formation of the title compounds 1 and 2, respectively, which were purified by column chromatography over silica gel using ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (2 : 3). The identity of the alkamides 1 and 2 was established through their spectral data which are comparable to those reported in literature¹.

Experimental

Ir spectra (film) of compounds were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CCl₄) on a Varian EM-390 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. Silica gel (ASC, Bombay) impregnated with CaSO₄ was used for tlc. Unless otherwise stated, all organic extracts were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate.

2(*Z*)-Octen-1-ol (4) : Oct-2-yn-1-ol (3; 6.0 g, 47.6 mmol) containing Lindlar's catalyst (0.8 g) in dry *n*-hexane was stirred under hydrogen gas atmosphere, when one equivalent of hydrogen was used up. The catalyst was then filtered off, the filtrate washed with water and dried. Removal of the solvent followed by chromatography over silica gel afforded the pure allylic alcohol (4; 5.1 g, 84%) (Found : C, 74.81; H, 12.42. C₈H₁₆O calcd. for : C, 74.94; H, 12.58%); ν_{\max} 3 400, 2 950, 2 865, 1 658, 1 030 and 730 cm⁻¹ (*cis* double bond); δ (CDCl₃) 0.9 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.3 (6H, m, saturated methylenes), 2.1 (2H, m, allylic methylene), 3.10 (1H, bs, OH exchangeable with D₂O), 4.20 (2H, d, CH₂OH) and 5.55 (2H, m, olefinic protons).

Oct-2(*E*)-en-1-ol (5) : The alcohol (4; 4.0 g, 31.2 mmol) in dry CH₂Cl₂ was added to a stirred suspension of PCC (10.13 g, 46.88 mmol) in dry CH₂-Cl₂ in a single lot at 5°. The stirring was continued for 3 h at low temperature. The reaction mixture was then diluted with ether (150 ml), filtered over neutral alumina and dried. Evaporation of the solvent yielded the aldehyde 5 (2.5 g, 66%) (Found : C, 75.92; H, 10.93. C₈H₁₄O calcd. for : C, 76.14; H, 11.18%); ν_{\max} 2 890, 2 730, 1 700, 1 640 and 970 cm⁻¹ (*trans* double bond); δ (CDCl₃) 0.9 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.3 (6H, m, saturated methylenes), 2.1 (2H, m, allylic methylene), 5.8 (2H, m, olefinic protons), 8.9 (1H, s, -CHO).

Ethyl 2*E*, 4*E*-decadienoate (6) : Dimethylethoxycarbonylmethyl phosphonate (4.6 g, 23.4 mmol) was added dropwise to a slurry of NaH (1.05 g, 50% emulsion in oil; 43.75 mmol) in dry THF at low temperature. After the addition, the reaction mixture was stirred till evolution of gas ceased and a clear solution formed. The aldehyde (5; 2.5 g, 19.84 mmol) in dry THF (10 ml) was added slowly to this clear solution at 10° and the reaction mixture was further stirred for 3 h at room temperature and for 3 h at 50°. The reaction mixture was then cooled, decomposed with cold water, extracted with ether and dried. Evaporation of the solvent followed by purification of the residue by column chromatography over silica gel yielded the ester (6; 2.5 g, 64%)

(Found : C, 73.15 ; H, 10.12. $C_{12}H_{20}O_2$ calcd. for : C, 73.43 ; H, 10.27%) ; ν_{max} 3 000–2 950, 1 725, 1 650, 1 620, 1 450, 1 230, 1 045, 1 005 and 980 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 0.8–1.1 (3H, t, CH_3), 1.2–1.6 (9H, m, saturated methylene and OCH_2CH_3), 2.1 (2H, m, allylic methylene), 4.3 (2H, m, $-\text{CO}-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2-$), 5.85 (1H, d, J 15.0 Hz, 2-H), 6.25 (1H, m, 4-H) and 6.9–7.5 (2H, m, 3-H and 5-H).

2E,4E-Decadien-1-oiic acid (7) : To a methanolic solution (40 ml) of the ester (6 ; 1 g, 5.10 mmol) was added a saturated solution of KOH (0.3 g, 5.36 mmol) in methanol and the contents were stirred for 10 h at room temperature. The alcohol was then evaporated, the residue treated with water (20 ml) and extracted with ether. The aqueous layer was then acidified with hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether (6 \times 30 ml). The combined ether extract was dried and the solvent evaporated to furnish the unsaturated acid (7 ; 0.68 g, 70%) (Found : C, 71.16 ; H, 9.41. $C_{10}H_{16}O_2$ calcd. for : C, 71.39 ; H, 9.59%) ; ν_{max} 3 000–3 400, 1 700, 1 645, 1 620, 1 420, 1 280, 1 000 and 730 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 0.9 (3H, t, CH_3), 1.32 (6H, m, saturated methylenes), 2.1–2.2 (2H, m, allylic methylene), 5.85 (1H, d, J 15 Hz, 2-H), 6.25 (1H, m, 4-H), 6.9–7.6 (2H, m, 3-H and 5-H) and 10.8 (1H, s, COOH).

N-(2E,4E-Decadienoyl)pyrrolidine (2) : To a solution of 7 (0.4 g, 2.38 mmol), the pyrrolidine (0.154 g, 2.17 mmol) and triethylamine (0.437 g, 4.33 mmol) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (50 ml) at 0°, was added dropwise $POCl_3$ (0.365 g, 2.38 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (5 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h at 0° and another 1 h at room temperature. The contents were then poured in cold water and the organic layer separated, washed with saturated $NaHCO_3$ solution, water and dried. Evaporation of the solvent followed by chromatographic purification of the residue over silica gel afforded the pure amide (2 ; 0.3 g, 56%) (tlc single spot) (Found : C, 75.78 ; H, 10.29 ; N, 5.91. $C_{14}H_{23}NO$ calcd. for : C, 75.97 ; H, 10.47 ; N, 6.33%) ; ν_{max} 2 950, 2 940, 1 650, 1 630, 1 605, 1 440, 1 005 and 980 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 0.85 (3H, m, CH_3), 1.2–1.5 (6H, m, saturated methylenes), 1.79–2.02 (6H, m, allylic methylene and β,β' -hydrogens), 3.4–3.6 (4H, m, α and α' -hydrogens), 6.0 (1H, d, J 15 Hz, 2-H), 6.1–6.24 (2H, m, 4-H and 5-H) and 7.2 (1H, m, 3-H).

N-Isobutyl-(2E,4E-decadienamamide (1) : It was prepared in a similar way as 2 using the acid 7 (0.60 g, 3.57 mmol), isobutylamine (0.24 g, 3.29 mmol), triethylamine (0.66 g, 6.53 mmol) in dry CH_2Cl_2 and $POCl_3$ (0.55 g, 3.58 mmol). Usual work up and chromatographic purification of the residue afforded the amide (1 ; 0.5 g, 67%) (Found : C, 75.04 ; H, 11.14 ; N, 5.96. $C_{14}H_{25}NO$ calcd. for : C, 75.28 ; H, 11.28 ; N, 6.27%) ; ν_{max} 3 070, 3 000, 1 655, 1 625, 1 550, 1 265, 1 005, 790 and 770 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 0.9 (9H, m, CH_3 , $CH(CH_3)_2$), 1.32 (6H, m, saturated methylenes), 1.8–2.2 (3H, m, allylic methylene and $CH_2CH(CH_3)_2$), 3.1–3.3 (2H, t, $NHCH_2$), 5.5 (1H, br s, NH), 6.0 (1H, d, J 15.0 Hz,

2-H), 6.2 (2H, m, 4-H and 5-H) and 7.27 (1H, m, 3-H).

References

1. K. LIKHITWITAYAWUID, N. RVANGRUNGSI, G. L. LANGE and C. P. DECICCO, *Tetrahedron*, 1987, 3689
2. L. CROMBIE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 999.
3. C. K. ATAL, K. L. DHAR and J. SINGH, *Lloydia*, 1975, 38, 256.
4. E. V. ERMILOVA, L. A. REMIZOVA, I. A. FAVORSKAYA and N. L. TREGUBOVA, *J. Org. Chem. USSR (Engl. Transl.)*, 1975, 11, 517.
5. H. LINDLAR and R. DUBUIS, *Org. Synth.*, 1973, 5, 880
6. E. J. COREY and J. W. SUGGS, *Tetrahedron Lett.* 1975, 2647
7. W. S. WADSWORTH and W. D. EMMONS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 1733.

A New Synthesis of Polychlorobibenzyls†

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COUPLING reactions of alkyl halides under homogeneous and heterogeneous conditions are well-known¹⁻⁴. Diarylmethane dihalides (Ar_2CX_2) have been converted to tetraaryl alkenes ($Ar_2C=CAr_2$) with sodium selenide⁵ and iron pentacarbonyl⁶. 4-Nitrobenzyl chloride with potassium *t*-butoxide undergoes oxidative coupling to give 4,4'-dinitrostilbene via nucleophilic substitution followed by elimination⁷. With metallic iron⁸, copper⁹ and colloidal palladium¹⁰, benzotrichloride gives tetrachlorobibenzyl in aqueous medium. In this communication we report a new reagent sodium iodide which can couple activated alkyl halides to give polychlorobibenzyls.

Experimental

The coupling reaction was carried out by refluxing the alkyl chloride (α,α,α -trichlorotoluene or α,α -dichlorotoluene ; 10 mmol) in *N,N*-dimethylformamide or acetonitrile or 2-propanol (50 ml), with sodium iodide (50 mmol) for 1–4 h. The refluxate on dilution with water followed by decolourisation with sodium thiosulphate yielded the solid product which was crystallised from alcohol-chloroform mixture (1 : 1).

Results and Discussion

The reaction of activated polyhalide with iodide is presented in Scheme 1. There are two possible

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